

THE ACTION OF SODIUM ON ETHYL β -METHYLBUTANE $-\alpha\beta$ -TRICARBOXYLATE. PART V

BY RAM NARAYAN CHAKRAVARTI

The product of the sodium condensation of ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylate consists exclusively of ethyl 3-methylcyclopentane-1-one-3:5-dicarboxylate, since it can be converted into *cis*-1-methylcyclopentane-1:3-dicarboxylic acid unaccompanied by 1-methylcyclopentane-1:2-dicarboxylic acid.

In previous parts of this series (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 173, 189, 247) it has been shown that the product of the action of sodium on ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylate on treatment with appropriate reagents *in situ* furnishes the cyclopentanone ester (I, R=Me, Et, -CH₂-CO₂Et). The proof of the structure of (I) rests on the fact that on hydrolysis it gives either a tricarboxylic acid (II) or a ketonic acid (III) depending on the experimental conditions used.

In conformity with this view, the parent ester should possess the structure (I, R=H), since on reduction with sodium amalgam it gives the hydroxy-acid (IV). The ester of (IV) on treatment with phosphorus oxychloride and pyridine and subsequent hydrolysis yields the unsaturated acid (V), m.p. 168°.

In spite of careful search, however, no trace of the isomeric unsaturated acid (VI), m.p. 204°, (*cf.* Datta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 611), which is expected to be formed if the Dieckmann product had the alternative structure (VII) suggested by Baker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1548), could be detected.

The acid (V) on hydrogenation in presence of platinum oxide furnishes a mixture of saturated acids from which pure *cis*-1-methylcyclopentane-1:3-dicarboxylic acid, m.p. 96-97°, has been isolated through its anhydride, m.p. 81° (Toivonen, John, Sainio and Kunsinen, *Suomen*

Kem., 1935, 8, [B], 46; Toivonen, Veijola and Friberg, *ibid.*, 44). For the purpose of direct comparison, however, both the *cis*- and *trans*-modifications of 1-methylcyclopentane-1:3-dicarboxylic acid have been prepared from ethyl 3-methylcyclopentane-1-one-3 carboxylate (ester of III, R = H). The latter gives a cyanohydrin (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 19 3, 20, 246) which on dehydration and hydrolysis affords a mixture of isomeric products (V) and (VIII) m.p. 155-62°, which could not be separated. The mixture of acids, m.p. 155-62°, on catalytic hydrogenation yields *cis*- and *trans*-modifications of 1-methylcyclopentane-1:3-dicarboxylic acid melting at 96-97° and 114° respectively (*cf.* Toivonen, *loc. cit.*).

It follows therefore that the action of sodium on ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ tricarboxylate leads to the formation of ethyl 3-methylcyclopentane-1-one-3:5-dicarboxylate (I, R = H).

The study of the influence of substituents on the course of such reactions is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Conversion of the Dieckmann Product (I, R = H) into cis 1-methyl cyclopentane-1:3-dicarboxylic Acid

*Reduction of the Dieckmann Product (I, R = H) with Sodium Amalgam: Formation of 3-Oxy-1-methylcyclopentane-1:4-dicarboxylic Acid (IV).—*The product of sodium condensation of ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylate (Chakravarti, *loc. cit.*) was treated with ice-water and acidified with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The benzene layer was separated, washed with water, dried over calcium chloride and the benzene evaporated. The residual oil was then distilled in *vacuo*, b.p. 127°/3 mm.

To the above product (6 g.) dissolved in aqueous alcohol, stirred and cooled, sodium amalgam (200 g.) was added during 24 hours. During the course of the reduction a current of CO₂ was passed through the solution. After the reduction was complete the aqueous solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid, evaporated to dryness and the residue extracted with ether. The dry gummy product (5 g.), obtained on evaporation of the ether, was esterified by heating on a water-bath for 12 hours with absolute alcohol (20 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (1.5 c.c.). It was finally diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution and water and the solvent was then evaporated. The residual liquid on distillation gave ethyl 3-oxy-1-methylcyclopentane-1:4-dicarboxylate, b.p. 145°/5 mm., yield 3 g. (Found: C, 58.6; H, 8.0. C₁₂H₂₀O₄ requires C, 59.0; H, 8.19 per cent).

*Dehydration of the Hydroxy-ester (as IV): Formation of 1-Methyl- Δ^4 -cyclopentene-1:3-dicarboxylic Acid (V) by Hydrolysis of the Product.—*The above hydroxy ester (2.7 g.) was heated to 140-145° for 1 hour with phosphorous oxychloride (10 c.c.) and dry pyridine (40 c.c.). It was then cooled in ice, decomposed with ice-water, acidified with hydrochloric acid, saturated with salt and extracted with ether. The crude oil obtained on evaporation of the ether was hydrolysed by heating on the water-bath for 1 hour with 10% aqueous alcoholic potash (60 c.c.).

The alcohol was then evaporated off with the addition of water and the solution acidified with hydrochloric acid when the sparingly soluble unsaturated acid gradually separated out, yield 1 g. After one crystallisation from water (using charcoal) it melted at 168°. (Found: C, 56.1; H, 5.87. $C_8H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 56.4; H, 5.88 per cent).

Catalytic Reduction of the above Unsaturated Acid: Formation of 1-Methylcyclopentane-1:3-dicarboxylic Acid.—The above acid (0.6 g.) was reduced by shaking in an atmosphere of hydrogen in acetic acid solution in presence of platinum oxide (0.05 g.). 98 C.c. of hydrogen were absorbed in 10 minutes at 28° and then the absorption stopped completely. The solution was then filtered and the acetic acid evaporated off completely. The dry solid (0.5 g.) was treated with acetyl chloride (1 c.c.) and kept overnight. It was then evaporated to dryness in a vacuum desiccator over caustic potash. The finely powdered residue was cooled to 0° and treated with cold 5% sodium carbonate solution. After five minutes it was filtered and crystallised (0.28 g.) from petroleum ether in small colourless needles, m.p. 81°, undepressed when admixed with the anhydride of *cis*-1-methylcyclopentane-1:3-dicarboxylic acid prepared through the cyanohydrin of 3-methylcyclopentane-1-one-3-carboxylate (ester of III, R=H). (Found: C, 62.2; H, 6.6. $C_8H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 62.3; H, 6.5 per cent).

The pure anhydride was hydrolysed by heating with water and evaporating the clear solution. The residue, thus obtained, crystallised from water and was found to be identical with *cis*-1-methylcyclopentane-1:3-dicarboxylic acid, m.p. 96-97°, mixed melting point with the authentic sample of the *cis*-acid (*vide infra*).

The sodium carbonate extract on acidification gave an acid too small in quantity to be identified with the *trans*-acid.

Synthesis of cis- and trans-1-Methylcyclopentane-1:3-dicarboxylic Acid from Ethyl 3-Methylcyclopentane-1-one-3-carboxylate (Ester of III, R=H)

Ethyl 3-methylcyclopentane-1-one-3-carboxylate, required for the purpose, was obtained according to Ruzicka by the sodium condensation of ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylate and hydrolysis and subsequent esterification of the condensation product.

Cyanohydrin of ethyl 3-Methylcyclopentane-1-one-3-carboxylate was prepared by adding the above keto-ester (5 g.) drop by drop to cold liquid hydrogen cyanide, obtained by treating potassium cyanide (10 g.) with sulphuric acid (10 c.c. conc. acid and 10 c.c. water), the condensation being brought about in presence of a drop of potassium cyanide solution. It was then kept overnight at a low temperature. The cyanohydrin formed was stabilised by adding a drop of concentrated sulphuric acid and the excess of hydrogen cyanide was removed under suction.

Dehydration and Hydrolysis of the Cyanohydrin: Formation of a Mixture of (V) and (VIII).—The crude cyanohydrin, obtained above, was refluxed in an oil-bath at 140-45° for 1 hour with phosphorous oxychloride (23 c.c.) and pyridine (84 c.c.). Excess of oxychloride was decomposed by cooling in ice and adding ice-water drop by drop. The solution was then acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid (45 c.c.) and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water and the ether evaporated. The residual unsaturated nitrile was hydrolysed by heating on the sand-bath for 24 hours with concentrated hydrochloric acid (60 c.c.). The sparingly soluble unsaturated acid was then obtained by filtering the cold solution, yield 3 g. It is soluble in hot water and crystallises slowly on cooling, m.p. 155-62°.

The acid, thus obtained, is probably a mixture of (V) and (VIII). (Found: C, 56.2; H, 5.8. $C_8H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 56.4; H, 5.88 per cent).

cis- and *trans*-1-Methylcyclopentane-1:3-dicarboxylic Acid.—The above product (2.04 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (35 c.c.) and shaken with platinum oxide (0.05 g.) in an atmosphere of pure hydrogen under normal pressure and at the room temperature (27°). 320 C.c. of hydrogen (cal. 318 c.c.) were absorbed in 20 minutes. The acetic acid solution was filtered and the acetic acid evaporated off completely (last traces in *vacuo* over caustic potash). The crude acid, thus obtained, was treated with acetyl chloride (3 c.c.) and kept overnight. It was then evaporated to dryness in *vacuo* over caustic potash. The solid product (1.2 g.) was finely powdered, added to 5% sodium carbonate solution at 0° and after 5 minutes filtered and the anhydride of *cis*-1-methylcyclopentane-1:3-dicarboxylic acid crystallised from ligroin in small needles, m.p. 81° (0.85 g.). (Found: C, 62.0; H, 6.5. $C_8H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 62.3; H, 6.5 per cent).

The sodium carbonate extract, obtained above, was acidified with hydrochloric acid and evaporated to dryness on the water-bath. The residue was extracted with ether and the ether evaporated when an impure acid (0.25 g.) was obtained. From this *pure trans*-1-methylcyclopentane-1:3-dicarboxylic acid, m.p. 114°, was obtained after repeated crystallisations from water.

The *pure cis*-anhydride (0.4 g.) was hydrolysed by heating with water on a sand-bath for 1 hour when a clear solution was obtained. It was then evaporated to dryness and the residue crystallised from water when *pure cis*-1-methylcyclopentane-1:3-dicarboxylic acid was obtained, m.p. 96-97°. (Found: C, 55.5; H, 6.9. $C_8H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 55.8; H, 6.9 per cent).

My grateful thanks are due to Dr. J. C. Bardhan for the facilities given to me and for his kind advice and criticism.